

اصحاب صفہ کی عملی خدمات کا ایک تحقیقی جائزہ

An Exploratory Review of the Practical Services of Ashaab-e-Suffah

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Abstract

In the history of the rise and fall of nations, if one searches for one of the most effective history-making factors, it can be said without a doubt that education comes first. This is the reason why Allah appointed man as his caliph and representative on earth, the first thing he equipped him with was knowledge, and the task he assigned to all his prophets was the centrality of learning the book, wisdom and self-purification. Got it Many attempts have been made in the past years to understand the relationship between education and Islam and to create a true Islamic spirit in the educational system. As soon as one hears the name of Suffah and the companions of Suffah, the mind travels in the world of imagination and stops at the canopy or hut which was situated at the north-east corner of the Prophet's Mosque. Who had no house, no door, no land. Dar-e-Arqam was an Islamic training center in Makkah. Muslims used to pray, learn the Qur'an and receive training in religious and worldly matters under the guidance of the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him). If Madinah became the center of Islam, then it was going to have the honor of becoming the center of the Islamic state. Bait al-Maqdis was the Qibla for the first sixteen months of Madani's life. When Baitullah was declared as the Qiblah, the wall of the previous Qiblah was still standing on the back side of the Prophet's Mosque. Rasulullah's Heli ordered to put a canopy over it. He was named Suffah or Zillah. Apart from this roof, there was no wall around it. The status of the educational institution of Suffah was that of a residential seminary of that period. Where the travelers and poor students were equipped with fine education. In the educational institution of Suffah, the Messenger of Allah was actually preparing human capital. Limited research work has been done. The importance of this research to develop the education and training system of Suffah on Islamic lines is undeniable.

Keywords: Training System, Ashab-e- Suffah, Caliph, Dar-e-Arqam, educational institution.

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